

Action of Hydrazides. Part II. Synthesis of some Bis-triazoles from Thiocarbo- and Carbo-hydrazides.

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In a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1927, 4, 180) it was shown that thiocarbohydrazide condensed with phenanthraquinone and its monoxime yielding respectively a red hydrazone and a red bis-triazole derivative. In the present communication the hydrazide has been coupled with a number of derivatives of the quinone and its monoxime with a view to observe the effect of substitution in the phenanthrene ring by bromine atom and nitro group on the colour of the hydrazones and the triazoles ; and as a result it has been found that these atoms or groups have very little influence on the colour of the compounds produced.

Owing to the interesting results obtained in the foregoing cases it has been thought desirable to study the action of carbohydrazide on the various derivatives of phenanthraquinone and its monoximes and thus to draw a comparison of colour between the series of compounds which differ in having a sulphur atom in one and an oxygen atom in the other. The colour of the oxygen containing compounds are found to be mostly yellow while those of the sulphur containing compounds are red. The former are, therefore, apparently lighter in colour than the latter. The natural conclusion is that the tendency of the sulphur atom is to deepen the colour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of Thiocarbohydrazide with Substituted Phenanthraquinones and their Monoximes.

Di-(2-bromophenanthraquinone)-thiocarbohydrazone.—2-Bromophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid for a few minutes ; the precipitated thiocarbohydrazone was washed with water and crystallised from pyridine in red needles, m. p. 236°. (Found: N, 8·82. $C_{20}H_{16}O_2N_4SBr_2$ requires N, 8·69 per cent.).

2-Thio keto-bis-(5-bromophenanthro-1 : 2 : 3-triazole).—2-Bromophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for about half an hour. The triazole separated on long standing ; this was collected and crystallised from acetic acid in red microscopic needles, m. p. 145°. (Found : N, 13·24. $C_{20}H_{14}N_6SBr_2$ requires N, 13·16 per cent.)

Di-(2:7-dibromophenanthraquinone)-thiocarbohydrazone.—2:7-Dibromophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride in acetic acid solution yielded at once the thiocarbohydrazone. This was crystallised from pyridine in brown-red needles, m. p. 260°. (Found : N, 7·12. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2N_4SBr_2$ requires N, 6·98 per cent.)

2-Thio keto-bis-(5 : 10-dibromophenanthro-1 : 2 : 3-triazole).—2:7-Dibromophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride in acetic acid solution gave the triazole separating in orange crystals. Crystallised from acetic acid it forms orange needles, m. p. 210°. (Found : N, 10·70. $C_{20}H_{14}N_6SBr_2$ requires N, 10·55 per cent.)

Di-(2-nitrophenanthraquinone)-thiocarbohydrazone.—2-Nitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution. The hydrazone separated was crystallised from acetic acid in dull red needles, m. p. 220°. (Found : N, 14·62. $C_{20}H_{10}O_6N_6S$ requires N, 14·50 per cent.)

2-Thio keto-bis-(5-nitrophenanthro-1 : 2 : 3-triazole).—2-Nitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for one hour. The solution on cooling was diluted with water when the triazole was precipitated as a dirty brown amorphous powder. It was crystallised from alcohol in brown microscopic rectangles, m. p. 200°. (Found : N, 19·57. $C_{20}H_{14}O_4N_6S$ requires N, 19·65 per cent.)

Di-(4-nitrophenanthraquinone)-thiocarbohydrazone.—4-Nitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for two hours. The hydrazone was precipitated from solution with water and the precipitate crystallised from alcohol in vermilion red needles, m. p. 155°. (Found : N, 14·55. $C_{20}H_{10}O_6N_6S$ requires N, 14·50 per cent.)

Di-(4 : 5-dibromophenanthraquinone)-thiocarbohydrazone.—4 : 5-Dibromophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid when the hydrazone separated in orange red crystals. This was crystallised from pyridine in rectangles of the same colour. It turns black at 260° and melts at 270°. (Found : N, 7·19. $C_{20}H_{14}N_4SO_2Br_2$ requires N, 6·98 per cent.)

2-Thioketo-bis-(7:8-dibromophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—4:5-Dibromophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid. The precipitated triazole was purified by crystallisation from pyridine in red rectangles, m. p. 235°. (Found: N, 10·68. $C_{10}H_4N_6SBr_2$ requires N, 10·55 per cent.)

Di-(4:5-dinitrophenanthraquinone)-thiocarbohydrazone.—4:5-Dinitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for one to two hours. The hydrazone precipitated with water was crystallised from alcohol in red microscopic rectangles, m. p. 162°. (Found: N, 16·92. $C_{10}H_4O_2N_8S$ requires N, 16·81 per cent.)

2-Thioketo-bis-(7:8-dinitrophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—4:5-Dinitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for one hour. The solution was diluted with water and the precipitate crystallised from alcohol in brown rectangles, m. p. 160°. (Found: N, 21·34. $C_{11}H_4O_2N_{10}S$ requires N, 21·21 per cent.)

Di-(2:7-dinitrophenanthraquinone)-thiocarbohydrazone.—2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid for a quarter of an hour and the triazole precipitated with water was crystallised from alcohol in rectangles of dark colour, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 16·62. $C_{10}H_4O_2N_8S$ requires N, 16·81 per cent.)

2-Thioketo-bis-(5:10-dinitrophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for an hour and the precipitated triazole was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in red needles which turn black at 250° and do not melt at 295°. (Found: N, 21·26. $C_{10}H_4O_2N_{10}S$ requires N, 21·21 per cent.)

Carbohydrazide and the Derivatives of Phenanthraquinone and their Monoximes.

Diphenanthraquinone-carbohydrazone.—Phenanthraquinone and carbohydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution when the hydrazone separated immediately. This was collected and crystallised from pyridine in orange yellow needles, m. p. 285°. (Found: N, 11·86. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 11·81 per cent.)

2-Keto-bis-(phenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—Phenanthraquinone monoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic

acid solution for two hours. The separated triazole was crystallised from pyridine in bright yellow rectangles, m.p. 272°. (Found: N, 18·21. $C_{20}H_{11}ON_3$ requires N, 18·10 per cent.).

Di-(2-bromophenanthraquinone)-carbohydrazone.—2-Bromophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for half an hour. The solution was diluted with water and the precipitated triazole was crystallised from alcohol in brown rectangles, m. p. 275°. (Found: N, 9·03. $C_{20}H_{11}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires N, 8·92 per cent.).

2-Keto-bis-(5-bromophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole)—2-Bromophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride in acetic acid solution were heated for twenty minutes. The precipitated triazole that separated (a further quantity being obtained on cooling) was crystallised from acetic acid in brown needles, m. p. 245°. (Found: N, 13·64. $C_{20}H_{11}ON_6Br_2$ requires N, 13·51 per cent.).

Di-(2-nitrophenanthraquinone)-carbohydrazone.—2-Nitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride in acetic acid solution were heated only for a few minutes when the hydrazone separated. This was collected and crystallised from nitrobenzene in brown rectangles, m. p. 280°. (Found: N, 15·14. $C_{20}H_{10}O_7N_2$ requires N, 15·00 per cent.).

2-Keto-bis-5-nitrophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole.—2-Nitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution, the triazole beginning to separate almost immediately. After ten minutes the solution was filtered and the residue was crystallised from acetic acid in greenish yellow needles, m. p. 192°. (Found: N, 20·30. $C_{20}H_{10}O_6N_6$ requires N, 20·22 per cent.).

Di-(4-nitrophenanthraquinone)-carbohydrazone.—4-Nitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution. After five minutes the separated crystals were filtered and crystallised from pyridine in yellow needles, which turn red at 190° and melt at 240°. (Found: N, 15·12. $C_{20}H_{10}O_7N_2$ requires N, 15·00 per cent.).

2-Keto-bis-(7-nitrophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—4-Nitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for forty-five minutes. The triazole separated in greenish yellow needles, m. p. 200°, which were found to be insoluble in all solvents. (Found: N, 20·33. $C_{20}H_{10}O_6N_6$ requires N, 20·22 per cent.).

Di-(2:7-dibromophenanthraquinone)-carbohydrazone.—2:7-Dibromophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for twenty minutes, the hydrazone separating in orange red needles. These were crystallised from nitrobenzene. It turns red at 280° and melts at 295°. (Found: N, 7.34. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires N, 7.12 per cent.).

2-Keto-bis-(5:10-dibromophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—2:7-Dibromophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride in acetic acid solution were heated for half an hour. The solution was diluted with water and the precipitated triazole was crystallised from alcohol in orange rectangles, m. p. 210°. (Found: N, 10.89. $C_{16}H_{12}ON_6Br_2$ requires N, 10.76 per cent.).

Di-(2:7-dinitrophenanthraquinone)-carbohydrazone.—2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution when the hydrazone separated in dirty yellow crystals. This was recrystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow microscopic rectangles, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 17.48. $C_{16}H_{12}O_{11}N_8$ requires N, 17.23 per cent.).

2-Keto-bis-(5:10-dinitrophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for fifteen minutes. The solution on cooling was filtered from the solid residue which was crystallised from acetic acid in greenish yellow needles, m. p. 230°. (Found: N, 21.87. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6N_{10}$ requires N, 21.74 per cent.).

Di-(2:5-dinitrophenanthraquinone)-carbohydrazone.—4:5-Dinitrophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution. The hydrazone was crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow rectangles, m. p. 295°. (Found: N, 17.82. $C_{16}H_{14}O_{11}N_8$ requires N, 17.23 per cent.).

2-Keto-bis-(7:8-dinitrophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—4:5-Dinitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid for twenty minutes. After cooling the solution was diluted with water and the precipitated triazole was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 160°. (Found: N, 21.65. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6N_{10}$ requires N, 21.74 per cent.).

Di-(4:5-dibromophenanthraquinone)-carbohydrazone.—4:5-Dibromophenanthraquinone and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid. The hydrazone was crystallised from pyridine in reddish yellow rectangles, m. p. above 300°. (Found: N, 7.25. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_2Br_2$ requires N, 7.12 per cent.).

2-Keto-bis-(7:2-dibromophenanthro-1:2:3-triazole).—4:5-Dibromophenanthraquinonemonoxime and the hydrazide hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution for ten minutes and the separated triazole was crystallised from pyridine in yellow rectangles, m. p. 273°. (Found: N, 10·82. $C_{20}H_{14}ON_6Br_4$ requires N, 10·76 per cent.).

My thanks are due to Prof. J. C. Ghosh and Dr. P. C. Guha for their kind interest and encouragement during the course of this investigation.

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Received April 11, 1928.